

Heterocyclic Quinones : Part I—Synthesis of Benzo(1:2-b, 4:5-b') dibenz(f,f')-Pyrrocoline Quinones

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A series of unsymmetrical disubstituted benzo(1:2-b), 4:5-b'-dibenz(f, f')-pyrrocoline quinones has been synthesised by condensing chloranil with active methylene compounds and isoquinoline which gave only the trans form of the compound as shown by colour reaction and T.L.C. The deep colour of these compounds is attributed to the betaine structure as one of the contributing form.

TILAK and VENKITESWARAN^{1,2} have reported a method for the preparation of pyrrocoline quinones from chloranil and 2:3 dichloro-1:4 naphthoquinone. Several compounds containing a reactive methylene group were reacted with chloranil and pyridine and in each case a pair of corresponding 5,11-disubstituted benzo(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dipyrrocoline-6:12-quinone and 5,7-disubstituted-benzo(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dipyrrocoline-6:12-quinone as geometrical isomers was obtained³. Considering the evidences^{2,3,4} leading to the above structures, it seemed interesting to carry out the reaction of chloranil and reactive methylene compounds with isoquinoline, with the hope of obtaining benzo(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(f, f') pyrrocoline 8,16-quinones.

Interaction of chloranil, acetoacetic ester and isoquinoline gave compound (A), m.p. 328-30°. It gave a brilliant blue colour in conc. H₂SO₄ which turned red with precipitation on basification and the blue colour reappeared on addition of conc. H₂SO₄. This indicates that only the transform is obtained and is actually 7,15 dicarbethoxy-benzo(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(f, f')-pyrrocoline-8:16-quinone. The compound gives beautiful pink colour with fluorescence in benzene.

Similarly with malonic ester, the same compound (A) is obtained. m.p. 327-29° confirmed through TLC.

Interaction of I with acetyl acetone and benzoyl acetone in presence of isoquinoline gave compounds (B) and (C) respectively. Their structures have been

established by colour reactions (as in the case of (A)) as 7:15-diacetyl-benzo(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(f, f')-pyrrocoline-8:16-quinone and 7:15-dibenzoyl-benzo(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(f, f')-pyrrocoline-8:16-quinone respectively.

(B) R = COCH₃
(C) R = COC₆H₅

The colour reactions of the said compounds indicate that the products should have a trans-configuration, which is the only product isolated in this case. The formation of cis structure seems to be sterically hindered.

Interaction of I, methyl cyanide and isoquinoline gave a yellow coloured product, which could be extracted into chloroform giving a yellow coloured solution which was decolorized on acidification with dil. HCl. It however did not give the above colour reactions and was found to be the inner salt (the betaine)⁵ represented by (D). The compound does not melt up to 356°, and was crystallized from glacial acetic acid.

TABLE-1. 7:15 DISUBSTITUTED-BENZO(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-DIBENZ(f, f') PYRROCOLINE-QUINONES

where, R₁ = -COOEt,
-COCH₃, -COC₆H₅

Sl. No.	Active methylene compound used	Molecular formula	Crystallized from	Colour	M.P. °C	Elemental Analysis					
						Found			Required		
						C %	H %	N %	C %	H %	N %
1.	Ethyl acetoacetate	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆	Benzene	Red	328-30	72.4	4.0	5.1	72.4	4.1	5.2
2.	Malonic ester	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆	Benzene	Brown-red	327-29	72.3	4.1	5.2	72.4	4.1	5.2
3.	Acetyl acetone	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄	Pyridine	Brown	does not melt up to 356	76.5	3.7	5.9	76.5	3.8	5.9
4.	Benzoyl acetone	C ₄₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄	Pyridine	Dark-red	does not melt up to 356	80.7	3.6	4.5	80.8	3.6	4.6

Experimental Procedure

All melting points have been determined on a Kofler instrument and are uncorrected. General procedure adopted for the preparation of the benzo-(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(f, f')-pyrrocoline quinone is as given below:—

A mixture of chloranil (0.1 mole) reactive methylene compound (0.1 mole) and isoquinoline (0.1 mole) in 25-30 ml absolute alcohol was heated under reflux on a water bath for 4 hrs., when all the chloranil dissolved and a deeply coloured reaction mixture was obtained. The product separated on cooling was filtered and washed with ethanol, ether, hot water and then dried. The product was recrystallized from the desired solvent.

All these quinones so prepared were mostly soluble in benzene, dioxane, pyridine and less soluble in acetone and alcohol. They are insoluble in water. They gave blue to violet coloured solution in concentrated sulphuric acid which turned red on basification followed by precipitation. They also give a beautiful pink to pink red colour in benzene showing fluorescence. Analysis of the various benzo-(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz(f, f')-pyrrocoline-quinones prepared are described in Table 1.

Mechanism

The reaction mechanism for the formation of 7:15 disubstituted benzo(1:2-b, 4:5-b')-dibenz-

(f, f')-pyrrocoline quinones is based on a similar study⁶ done on the reaction of active methylene compounds with 2:3 dichloro 1:4 naphthoquinone and corroborates the process of cleavage of the more electron withdrawing group R during the final stage of cyclisation.

Dyeing Properties :

The dyeing characteristics of these compounds is under investigation.

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